

A Study of Hematological and Lipid Profile Status of Apparently Healthy Donors in Blood Bank at a Tertiary Care Centre in North India: A 2 Year Experience

Deeksha Singh¹, Sayeedul Hasan Arif², Suhail Ur Rehman³, Bhuvan Adhlakha⁴, Shivani Kalhan⁵, Samridhi Allhabadi⁶

¹Senior Resident, Government Institute of Medical Sciences, Greater Noida

²Professor, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College, AMU

³Assistant Professor, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College, AMU

⁴Assistant Professor, Government Institute of Medical Sciences, Greater Noida

⁵Professor, Government Institute of Medical Sciences, Greater Noida

⁶Senior Resident, Government Institute of Medical Sciences, Greater Noida

Received: 24-09-2022 / Revised: 26-10-2022 / Accepted: 09-11-2022

Corresponding author: Dr Deeksha Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Blood donation is a noble act and it saves the life of four patients, as one whole blood is divided into four components. Blood donation is a noble act for survival of the sick and needy patients during emergency. Numerous studies have been conducted and they have reported, the mean haemoglobin level, serum iron, serum ferritin and cholesterol level were significantly low in repeat donors compared to first time donors. Iron deficiency was more common in high frequent donors compared to low frequent donors [4]. There is strong evidence of the role of red cell indices as early indicators of iron diminution in frequent blood donors by measuring serum ferritin or soluble transferrin receptor levels.

Methods: This two year prospective study was done in the blood bank of J.N. Medical College and Hospital, AMU, Aligarh from 2018 to 2020. This study was conducted on first time donor, repeat donor and repeat donor on subsequent donation. Statistical analysis of Haematological parameters, Iron Profile and Lipid Profile was done.

Results: In present study, there was decrease in value of haemoglobin in repeat donors (13.4g/dL) which further decreases on subsequent donation (13.36g/dL). Mean iron in first time donor was 92.67µg/dL which reduces on repeat donation and on subsequent donation. The value of mean iron reduces from 90.9µg/dL in repeat donors to 83.3µg/dL in repeat donors on subsequent donation. Mean ferritin value in first time donor was 59.47 ng/mL and in repeat donors it was 51.17 ng/mL which further reduces to 43.08 ng/mL on subsequent donation. LDL cholesterol in first time donor was 74.77 mg/dL and it decreases in repeat donors and in repeat donor on subsequent donation to 70.7 mg/dL and 65.5 mg/dL respectively. LDL/HDL ratio in first time donor was 2.19 and it reduces to 2.15 in repeat donors and on further donation it falls to 2.11.

Conclusion: Blood donation is beneficial as it reduces LDL cholesterol and increases HDL cholesterol.

Keyword: Haematological parameters, Blood donors, Voluntary blood donation, Lipid Profile

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

“Safe blood starts with me, Blood saves lives” was the WHO theme for 2000 AD. Blood donation is a noble act and a single whole blood unit can save the life of four patients, and is also used in numerous therapeutic and preventive etiologies [1].

In 1667, the very first animal to human transfusion of blood was conducted [2] and James Blundell in 1818, conducted the first human to human transfusion. The first blood donation facility in the world was established in London by Percy Oliver in 1921. Most of the respondents stated that adequate information and the knowledge that a unit of blood donated will save life would encourage them to be voluntary donors [3]. Numerous studies conducted and they have reported, the mean haemoglobin level, serum iron, serum ferritin and cholesterol level were significantly low in repeat donors compared to first time donors. Iron deficiency was more common in high frequent donors compared to low frequent donors [4]. There is strong evidence of the role of red cell indices as early indicators of iron diminution in frequent blood donors by measuring serum ferritin or soluble transferrin receptor levels [5]. Serum ferritin level indicates body iron stores can be reduced to halved through donation of single unit of whole blood [6].

Therefore donation of whole blood reduces risk of atherosclerosis in donor [7]. There is beneficial effects of blood donation in its relationship with ischemic heart disease. Blood donors compared to non-donors

seemed to have more favourable lipoprotein concentrations, like lower LDL cholesterol concentration or apoB, lower triglyceride levels, elevated HDL cholesterol concentration, and lengthened lag times (oxidative resistance or oxidative potential) of VLDL [8]. Among regular blood donors the level of serum cholesterol, phospholipids, and esterified fatty acid levels are significantly lower compared to non-donors [9].

Materials and Methods

A two year prospective study was done in the blood bank in north India from 2018 to 2020. The study was conducted on first time donor, repeat donor and repeat donor on subsequent donation. Statistical analysis of Haematological parameters, Iron Profile and Lipid Profile was done.

All results were statistically analysed by software SPSS 20 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) by applying paired t test and unpaired t test and p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Total number of 200 cases collected in which 120 (60%) were first time donors and 80 (40%) were repeat donors. Out of these 80 repeat donors, 31 (38.75%) were those donors who were followed up for subsequent donation. In our study, most of the donors were those who came to donate blood to their relatives during emergency and were first time donors.

Haemoglobin of donors

Table 1

First time donor (n=120)		Repeat donor (n=80)		Repeat donor on subsequent donation (n=31)	
Range of Hb (g/dL)	Mean Hb (g/dL)	Range of Hb (g/dL)	Mean Hb (g/dL)	Range of Hb(g/dL)	Mean Hb (g/dL)
12.6-15.3	13.513±0.64	12.6-15.9	13.4±0.83	12.6-15.4	13.36±0.9

Mean haemoglobin of first time donors is 13.5 which reduces on repeat donation and further reduces on subsequent donation as shown in table 1.

Iron of donors**Table 2**

First time donor (n=120)		Repeat donor (n=80)		Repeat donor on subsequent donation (n=31)	
Range of Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	Mean Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	Range of Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	Mean Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	Range of Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)	Mean Iron ($\mu\text{g/dL}$)
39-176	92.67 \pm 25.97	42.8-145	90.09 \pm 18.7	40.8-114	83.3 \pm 18.04

Mean value of iron in first time donors is 92.67 which reduces on repeat donation and further reduces on subsequent donation as shown in table 2.

Range and mean LDL of donor**Table 3**

First time donor (n=120)		Repeat donor (n=80)		Repeat donor on subsequent donation (n=31)	
Range of LDL (mg/dL)	Mean LDL (mg/dL)	Range of LDL (mg/dL)	Mean LDL (mg/dL)	Range of LDL (mg/dL)	Mean LDL (mg/dL)
30-145	74.77 \pm 22.76	34-145	70.7 \pm 22.0	31.7-119	65.5 \pm 20.39

Mean LDL of first-time donors is 74.77 which reduces on repeat donation and further reduces on subsequent donation as shown in table 3.

Range and MEAN HDL of donor**Table 4**

First time donor (n=120)		Repeat donor (n=80)		Repeat donor on subsequent donation (n=31)	
Range of HDL (mg/dL)	Mean HDL (mg/dL)	Range of HDL (mg/dL)	Mean HDL (mg/dL)	Range of HDL (mg/dL)	Mean HDL (mg/dL)
19-62	34.84 \pm 188.2	18-54	33.2 \pm 8.48	15-50	36.54 \pm 5.66

Mean HDL of first time donors is 34.84 which reduces on repeat donation but increased on repeated donation as shown in table 4 which is beneficial to donor.

LDL/HDL Ratio**Table 5**

First time donor (n=120)		Repeat donor (n=80)		Repeat donor on subsequent donation (n=31)	
Range of LDL/HDL	Mean LDL/HDL	Range of LDL/HDL	Mean LDL/HDL	Range of LDL/HDL (mg/dL)	Mean LDL/HDL (mg/dL)
4.53-1.03	2.19 \pm 0.63	3.5-1.2	2.15 \pm 0.60	3.5-1.0	2.11 \pm 0.41

Mean LDL/HDL ratio of first time donors is 2.19 which reduces on repeat donation and further reduces on subsequent donation as shown in table 5.

Discussion

In present study, haemoglobin reduces on repeat donation 42 and subsequent donation, though mean haemoglobin does not go below the normal limit of 12.5g/dL. It implies that repeat donation does not effect haemoglobin significantly. In addition this can be compensated by giving iron supplementation to the donors, if required. In a study done by Naidu *et al.*, 2013 [2] and Tailor *et al.*, 2017 [4] there was reduction in haemoglobin in repeat donor, the finding of which was similar to our study. However, Norashikin *et al* in 2006 [8], conducted study and he found out that haemoglobin increases on repeat donation which was discordant with our study.

Mean iron in first time donor was 92.67 μ g/dL which reduces on repeat donation and on subsequent donation. The value of mean iron reduces from 90.9 μ g/dL in repeat donors to 83.3 μ g/dL in repeat donors on subsequent donation, which was significant. It implies that with increase in number of donation, iron level falls down, but it does not reduces to the deficiency range. It means repeat donors which are donating regularly have reduced mean iron, which can be beneficial to the donors in terms of free radical injury and cardiovascular disease [10]. Similar study with similar findings that is reduction in iron on repeat donation was conducted by Tailor *et al* in 2017 [4], Abdullah *et al.*, 2011 [11].

In our study, LDL cholesterol in first time donor was 74.77 mg/dL and it decreases in repeat donors and in repeat donor on subsequent donation to 70.7 mg/dL and 65.5 mg/dL respectively. This reduction in LDL cholesterol was significant. In a study done by Bharadwaj R.S *et al* in 2005 [12], there was decrease in LDL cholesterol on repeat blood donation which was similar to the present study. Diminished release of nitric oxide into the arterial wall is associated with atherosclerosis, either because of reduced synthesis or excess degradation. Nitric oxide synthase is

controlled by iron through an iron regulatory protein: a cytoplasmic protein which regulates ferritin translation (Weiss G *et al.*, 1994).

We already know that, when body iron decreases, LDL particle become resistant to oxidation, so there is reduction in formation of oxidised LDL. Hence, there will be double benefit for the repeat donors in terms of both iron and LDL reduction, which will prevent donor from atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases. The progression of atherosclerosis involves inflammation of arteries and healing processes in a hyperlipemic environment, where low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation is the causal factor [14]. In our study HDL cholesterol was low in repeat donors (33.2 mg/dL) compared to first time donors (34.84 mg/dL). However, it increases to (36.54 mg/dL) on subsequent donation . So, repeat blood donation was beneficial, as it increases good HDL cholesterol and can prevent donors from atherosclerosis. Similar finding, to our study was found by Bharadwaj R.S., (2005) [12] in which HDL cholesterol increases on repeat blood donation which was concordant with our study.

LDL/HDL ratio in first time donor was 2.19 and it reduces to 2.15 in repeat donors and on further donation it falls to 2.11. Among all the parameters, plasma LDL/high-density lipoprotein (HDL) ratio was a better indicator of risk for coronary heart disease than either plasma LDL or HDL alone [15]. In a study done by Kinoshian B *et al.*, 1995 [16] he found out that change in LDL/HDL ratio was a better predictor for coronary heart disease risk than separate isolated levels of LDL and HDL. So by these findings we conclude that donating blood repeatedly reduces haemoglobin and other haematological parameters, but not to the level of deficient stage. And if any mild deficiency occur, we can counteract that by providing supplements. Repeat donation also reduces iron level, hence less free radical injury occur in body. It also

decreases total and LDL cholesterol (bad cholesterol), and increases HDL cholesterol (good cholesterol). Hence, repeated and frequent blood donation protect against the cardiovascular event by making the blood profile healthier.

References

1. Uche EI, Adediran A, Damulak OD, Adeyemo TA, Akinbami AA, Akanmu AS. Lipid profile of regular blood donors. *Journal of blood medicine*. 2013; 4:39-42.
2. Naidu DV, Raghu S, Vikram KN, Sai SN, Anudeepthi N, Meghana R. Study of Various Physiological, Biochemical and Hematological Parameters in Repeated Blood Donors. *MRIMS Journal of Health Sciences*. 2013;1(2).
3. Salaudeen AG, Odeh E. Knowledge and behavior towards voluntary blood donation among students of a tertiary institution in Nigeria. *Nigerian journal of clinical practice*. 2011;14(3):303-7.
4. Tailor HJ, Patel PR, Pandya AK, Mangukiya S. Study of various hematological parameters and iron status among voluntary blood donors. *International Journal of Medicine and Public Health*. 2017;7(1):61-65.
5. Garry PJ, Vander Jagt DJ, Wayne SJ, Koehler KH, Rhyne RL, Simon TL. A prospective study of blood donations in healthy elderly persons. *Transfusion*. 1991 Oct;31(8):686-92.
6. Finch CA, Cook JD, Labbe RF, Culala M. Effect of blood donation on iron stores as evaluated by serum ferritin. *Blood*. 1977;50(3):441-7.
7. Sullivan JL. Blood donation may be good for the donor: iron, heart disease, and donor recruitment. *Vox sanguinis*. 1991 Nov;61(3):161-4.
8. Salonen JT, Seppänen K, Nyyssönen K, Korpela H, Kauhanen J, Kantola M, Tuomilehto J, Esterbauer H, Tatzber F, Salonen R. Intake of mercury from fish, lipid peroxidation, and the risk of myocardial infarction and coronary, cardiovascular, and any death in eastern Finnish men. *Circulation*. 1995 Feb 1;91(3):645-55.
9. Susić D, B umer A. Serumlipid-und Harnsäurewerte von 177 Gelgenheitsblutspendern und 116 Patienten nach Myokardinfarkt. *Klinische Wochenschrift*. 1970 Jul 1; 48(14):847-52.
10. van Jaarsveld H, Pool GF. Beneficial effects of blood donation on high density lipoprotein concentration and the oxidative potential of low-density lipoprotein. *Atherosclerosis*. 2002 Apr 1;161(2):395-402.
11. Abdullah SM. The effect of repeated blood donations on the iron status of male Saudi blood donors. *Blood Transfusion*. 2011;9(2):167-171.
12. Bharadwaj RS. A study of lipid profiles among male voluntary blood donors in Chennai city. *Indian J Community Med*. 2005;30(1):16-17.
13. Weiss G, Werner-Felmayer G, Werner ER, Grünewald K, Wachter H, Hentze MW. Iron regulates nitric oxide synthase activity by controlling nuclear transcription. *The Journal of experimental medicine*. 1994 Sep 1;180(3):969-76.
14. Schwartz CJ, Valente AJ, Sprague EA, Kelley JL, Nerem RM. The pathogenesis of atherosclerosis: an overview. *Clinical cardiology*. 1991 Feb;14(S1):1-6.
15. Panagiotakos DB, Toutouzas PK. Importance of LDL/HDL cholesterol ratio as a predictor for coronary heart disease events in patients with heterozygous familial hypercholesterolaemia: a 15-year follow-up (1987-2002). *Current medical research and opinion*. 2003 Jan 1;19(2):89-94.
16. Kinoshian B, Glick H, Preiss L, Puder KL. Cholesterol and coronary heart disease: predicting risks in men by changes in levels and ratios. *Journal of investigative medicine: the official publication of the American Federation for Clinical Research*. 1995 Oct; 43(5): 443-50.